

Food and Chemical Toxicology

New formulation for producing salmon pâté with reduced sodium content

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Abstract:	Reducing consumption of salt, specifically sodium, is one of the most effective ways to improve public health. A novel formulation for producing salmon pâté with reduced sodium content was investigated. Salmon pâtés with three different sodium concentrations were evaluated using microbiological, sensory and chemical analyses. Saltwell®, a natural salt containing a mixture of sodium chloride and potassium chloride, was used for partial substitution of sodium chloride (table salt) alone in the formulation. Replacing 80 % of the sodium chloride with Saltwell®, resulted in a 22 % reduction in sodium, without affecting microbial activity or shelf-life. A trained sensory panel observed minor differences in three of the twelve sensory attributes that were evaluated (coherent texture, saltiness, canned fish flavor). However, these differences were weakly significant, and it is unlikely that consumers would identify these characteristics as unpalatable: evaluators in the trained sensory panel are much more sensitive to subtle differences in the products.
Response to Reviewers:	See detailed response to reviewers.

Reviewer #4: The paper is interesting, however some corrections, especially about microbiological analyses, have to be performed.

Abstract:

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The reviewers asked the authors to insert more results in the abstract, such as microbiology and shelf life results. I suggest that these results could be inserted. The last sentence of the abstract could be replaced by a sentence like "global acceptance tests should will be conducted with consumers to assess their perception of these parameters". Despite team's experience with sensory analysis, we cannot predict the perception of consumers, especially in products with reduced salt.

Speculation about the consumers' perception has been removed. A concluding sentence was also added to the abstract.

Introduction

Lines 34-35: Phrase "However, reduction of salt is a multi-dimensional task, since it can affect consumer acceptance and purchasing behaviour, microbial safety and shelf-life as well as processing techniques and product quality" repeats the same idea as the phrase in the previous paragraph "and it is a challenge for the food industry to reduce sodium concentrations in processed products, without compromising sensory properties (e.g. taste, flavor and texture), microbial safety, shelf-life and processability". I suggest removing the second sentence.

Second sentence has been deleted.

Materials and methods

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Item 2.1, line 11: I suggest replace the paragraph "Three pâtés" by "Three pâté formulations were produced, in three batches each, with different mixtures of salts (table 1)".

The wording has been changed according to the suggestion.

Item 2.1, after the Table 1: Please remove the period after the word "minutes".

I'm sorry but I can't see any period after the word "minutes".

Is it possible to insert the total (% or g) of salt in each pâté formulation?

A sentence explaining that the total salt content was 1.0 % (w/w) has been added.

Item 2.2, microbiological analyses: the methodology is confuse. I suggest rewriting and separate the physical-chemical analyses (pH, water activity and water content). Needless to say that it was performed under sterile conditions.

Suggestion: Pâtés were evaluated on day 0, 18, 22, 29, 36, 43 and 57, according to Nordic Committee on Food Analysis (2007; 2010; 2013). For shelf life study, packs were placed in an incubator at +8°C. Samples (25 g) were homogenized in 0.1% peptone solution. In addition, serial decimal dilutions were prepared from a 10⁻¹ dilution, as necessary. The plates were incubated on TSA at 30°C for 3 days for total aerobic counts; on MRS (De Man, Rogosa and Sharp, brand and city) at 25°C for 5 days, under anaerobic conditions, for lactic acid bacteria. Three replicates in each group were analyzed. The bacterial count results were expressed as log₁₀.

In order to study the product microbiological safety, a challenge test with two *Listeria monocytogenes* strains (CCUG 32964, which is used as a quality control strain in the food industry, and a natural strain - SIK609, isolated from fish in 2008 at RISE). The strains, maintained previously in a cryopreservation system, were replicated on TSA (Tryptone Soya Agar, brand and city) medium at 35°C for 24 hours. Then, they are separately in 9 mL of BHI (Brain Heart Infusion, brand and city) medium and incubated at 37°C for 20 hours. The strains were cold adapted in 9 mL BHI-broth at 15°C for 72 hours before being inoculated on to the surface of the pâtés as a mixture at 2.1-2.3 log CFU/g pâté using 0.25 mL inoculum per 25 g portion. The inoculated samples were repackaged, vacuum-sealed and stored as described previously. The counts of *Listeria monocytogenes* in inoculated pâtés homogenates were determined on days 0, 2, 4, 8, 10, 12, 14, 17, 21 and 28 and in uninoculated samples on days 0 and 57. *Listeria monocytogenes* were grown on Compass *Listeria* agar (brand and city) at 37°C for 24-48 hours.

Section 2.2 has been rewritten for clarification purposes. Water activity, water content and pH were included in the heading.

Why the microbiological analyses were conducted at times 0, 18, 22, 29, 36, 43 and 57, and chemical analyses were conducted only at times 0 and 70? Bacteria grows in an exponential curve, thus, analyses should be conducted at days intervals like 0, 10, 20, 40, 80.

Yes, bacteria grow in exponential curves but that doesn't mean that the sampling has to be done at certain intervals. You can still follow the growth. The sampling points were selected for practical purposes. Furthermore, in most cases microbiological analyses were carried out with a one week interval.

Item 2.3, table 2: I suggest improving the table formatting. Inserting another column with the scores, and merging the lines of the "Type of Observation" column. Please, insert "EN" before "ISO 13299:2016".

EN has been inserted before ISO instead of after. The same correction has been made in the reference list. The lines in the table have been merged, and the scores have been better indicated in the table legend.

Item 2.4, Chemical analyses:

Line 14: Please, remove "(AOAC, 2000)". It was cited below.

The citation has been deleted.

Item 2.5, statistical analyses:

What do you mean with "both technical and biological"?

Where are the others parameters? Chemical and physico-chemical?

Please, rewriting it.

The text has been rewritten to include physico-chemical analyses, and also to explain technical and biological replicates.

Results and discussion

Item 3.1, lines 1 and 2: Remove these lines. One contradicts the other.

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The lines have been deleted in order not to cause any confusion.

When the authors describe that "no sample presented TAC up to 7-7.5" is contrary to Figure 2. At 43 and 57 days of storage, Group C presented samples below 7-7.5, if the SD was included. It means that a replica has exceeded the established limits, and could cause health problems for consumer. I believe that the shelf life period is established based on the average, however, as there were only 3 samples, I recommend establishing a period of 36 days for security.

See answer to the last comment.

Item 3.1, line 9: remove the phrase "more than the expected eight weeks", because that shelf life was not described before in the manuscript.

See answer to the last comment.

Item 3.1, lines 10-14: Please, use lactic acid bacteria multiplication, because you are assessment the bacteria multiplication (CFU). The discussion about lactic acid bacteria must be changed. These bacteria are present in the seafood, but have an optimal incubation temperature of 37-40 degrees. Since your incubation was performed at 25 degrees, this may be a first problem. Another problem may be related to the analysis, if it was performed in triplicate, the count of latic bacteria should be similar in the replicates. The authors say it appeared in some samples, but did not describe details. There may have been a sampling error or even an error in the plating. Finally, some latic bacteria do not support salt concentrations above 5%. That is, depending on the salt concentration of the samples, this correlation can be made. I suggest rewriting that discussion or withdrawing that analysis due to the errors presented.

Regarding the choice of method, NMKL 140 is a standardized method that is widely used for enumeration of lactic acid bacteria in foods that can be spoiled by such microorganisms, e.g. meat and fish stored in vacuum or modified atmospheres. Since these samples were packaged in vacuum, this NMKL method that prescribes anaerobic incubation at 25°C was selected ahead of the ISO method that suggests aerobic incubation at 30°C. Another comment regards the salt concentrations in the samples; as has now been explained in other parts of the text, the salt concentration in the samples was 1.0 %, and thus did not exceed 5 %. Finally, details have been added about the sporadic occurrence of positive samples of lactic acid bacteria.

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Item 3.1, line 15: just use "L. monocytogenes", without "naturally occurring".

Has been deleted.

Item 3.1, Figure 2: please, choice "total aerobic counts" instead "naturally occurring bacteria". This term is not usual.

Has been changed.

The authors do not presented a graphic with Listeria or latic acid bacteria multiplication. Why? I suggest a line graphic with the 3 microorganisms analysed, with time correlation.

The growth of Listeria is already presented, see figure 6. Regarding lactic acid bacteria, it is explained in the text that such were only found in very few samples and thus no reliable growth curves could be established.

Item 3.1, lines after Figure 2: Start the paragraph with "There were no....". Remove the initial phrase. You must explain your results. The literature cited was contrary your work. Thus, I suggest, the authors search a paper that corroborate with your results.

The initial sentence has been deleted. However, the cited paper does corroborate with our results. In this study, ph was lower after 70 days, and in the cited paper it was reported that pH was reduced because of acid production by spoilage flora, the observations were similar.

Figure 3: there is no mid-gray in the graphic. The authors pasted the legend of the previous graph. Please correct it.
Figure 4: the same.
Figure 5: the same.

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The figure captions have been corrected.

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As commented by reviewer 1, it was not clear why this listeria challenge have to be made. The results showed a high multiplication of these bacteria. Where is the result of the samples without inoculation? Listeria is associated with food contamination and I see no justification for its inoculation in the pate, if the objective was sensorial and shelf life analyses.

Listeria is one of the two main risk organisms in this type of product, Clostridium botulinum being the other. Budget constraints meant that a selection had to be made and the choice fell on Listeria. The objective was to see if the growth of Listeria was affected by the different salt mixtures, which is why a test was performed with inoculated samples. The risk for contamination is discussed in detail and suggestions are made how to reduce the contamination risk.

Please, insert the statistical analyses results as variation coefficient and F values for each parameter.

The standard deviation is already indicated in figures 2-6. The variation coefficient (relative standard deviation) is not easily presented in such figures and therefore the absolute standard deviation is reported instead. As it says in the figure captions, in some cases the standard deviation was so small that it could not be visualized.

Table 3: In the lines of "Saltiness" and "Canned fish flavor", the letter B is missing or not?

No, the letter B is not missing. The letters indicate the samples that were significantly different. For these two attributes sample A was significantly different to sample C, while sample B was not significantly different to any of the other two samples.

There are no references in the discussion on sensory analysis. I suggest inserting works that corroborate the thesis that the mentioned differences would not cause problems of acceptance of the product by the consumer.

Sodium reduction in fish pâtés seems to be a novel area of research since no scientific papers on the subject have been found. Likewise, no peer-reviewed reports on the use of Saltwell as a means to reduce sodium levels have been found. There are some reports on Saltwell being used for the purpose in hamburgers, bread and some other products, but these reports have not been published in scientific journals. Instead, they are published on the webpage of the producer, and are not appropriate to refer to in this context. Thus, it is difficult to refer to any other studies that support the findings in this report.

Why the chemical and sensory analyzes were not performed during shelf life? Thus, we could evaluate the behavior of the protein related to texture and moisture. How can we guarantee a useful life without evaluating these parameters in the suggested times?

As in all studies there is a limit to the available resources. The aim of this work was to investigate if it was possible to produce salmon pâtés with lower sodium levels while maintaining microbiological safety and sensory quality. In order to ensure that there were no differences in microbial activity between the different samples it was necessary to study the microbial growth, i.e. analyses had to be carried out at different times during storage. However, regarding the sensory quality the question was if the different salt mixtures had any effect on the selected sensory attributes and this could be investigated by carrying out a single sensory analysis at the beginning of the storage period. Sensory quality might change during storage and there is a possibility that such changes could be different between the different samples. However, it was decided that it was more likely that any sensory differences could be attributed to differences in the formulations, i.e. already at the time of production.

I suggest removing the shelf life analysis and keeping only the formulation and analysis in zero time. There is no scientific parameters to fit pate shelf life.

We agree that the effort to estimate a shelf life is beyond the scope of this study and the text has therefore been amended to account for this. The objective of the work was to find out if the different salt mixtures had any effects on the microbiological quality (no effects were observed), sensory quality (minor differences were found for a three of the tested attributes), or the chemical composition (sodium and potassium levels differed between the samples). Thus, all discussions about shelf life have been removed.

Title

New formulation for producing salmon pâté with reduced sodium content

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Abstract

Reducing consumption of salt, specifically sodium, is one of the most effective ways to improve public health. A novel formulation for producing salmon pâté with reduced sodium content was investigated. Salmon pâtés with three different sodium concentrations were evaluated using microbiological, sensory and chemical analyses. Saltwell[®], a natural salt containing a mixture of sodium chloride and potassium chloride, was used for partial substitution of sodium chloride (table salt) alone in the formulation. Replacing 80 % of the sodium chloride with Saltwell[®], resulted in a 22 % reduction in sodium, without affecting microbial activity. A trained sensory panel observed minor differences in three of the twelve sensory attributes that were evaluated (coherent texture, saltiness, canned fish flavor). However, these differences were only weakly significant. Saltwell is a viable alternative to sodium chloride to produce seafood products with reduced sodium content without compromising quality and safety.

1 Introduction

Excess salt (sodium chloride, NaCl) consumption increases the risk of hypertension (high blood pressure) which is associated with increased risk of cardiovascular disease (Grillo et al., 2019). More specifically, high sodium intake is one of the most important health challenges in relation to processed food products. It affects public health in a negative manner leading to considerable economical costs for society (Global Burden of Disease, 2019), but salt is also a necessary ingredient for palatability and preservation. The World Health Organization (WHO) and national authorities worldwide have issued recommendations for sodium consumption, specifically that sodium intakes for adults and children should be less than 2 g sodium per day, which is equivalent to 5 g of sodium chloride (WHO, 2012). The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Panel on Nutrition, Novel Foods and Allergens (NDA) (2019) also considered that 2 g sodium per day is safe and adequate for the general adult population, but consumption in most European Member States is close to twice this. For this reason, WHO and EU have agreed a global target to reduce population sodium intake by 30 % until 2025 for the prevention and control of non-communicable diseases (WHO, 2018).

Approximately 75 % of the sodium intake originates from foods that are processed by the food industry or prepared for consumption in restaurants. The remainder (25 %) occurs naturally in foods or from salt added during cooking or at the table (Allison and Fouladkhah, 2018). In order to meet demands from both authorities and consumers, and be competitive, there is a strong need for the food industry to be able to offer reformulated products with lower sodium contents.

However, common or table salt is a crucial food ingredient that has many important functions, and it is a challenge for the food industry to reduce sodium concentrations in processed products, without compromising sensory properties (e.g. taste, flavour and texture), microbial safety, shelf-life and processability. The most obvious impact of salt is the salty taste, but it is also added for preservation. Salt lowers water activity, thereby affecting the growth of both spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms and, thus, extending shelf-life (Cepanec et al., 2017; Giese et al., 2019).

All unprocessed seafood contains some sodium at low concentrations. The sodium content of raw fish is typically 25-150 mg per 100 g (Pedro and Nunes, 2019). Sodium concentrations in processed seafoods vary substantially among products and countries, reflecting dietary habits and preferences. Large variations in salt contents can also be observed in foods from the same group, as is the case for salted and dried (around 2000-3000 mg per 100 g), canned (32-6000 mg per 100 g) and smoked (500-1100 mg per 100 g) fish products (Webster et al., 2010; Pedro and Nunes, 2019).

The application of well-defined strategies that might allow reduction of sodium in processed seafood products, while maintaining their quality, shelf-life, consumer acceptability and regulatory compliance, ~~are is~~ of utmost importance. ~~However, reduction of salt is a multi-dimensional task, since it can affect consumer acceptance and purchasing behaviour, microbial safety and shelf life as well as processing techniques and product quality.~~ Mineral salts, taste modifiers and taste enhancers as well as herbs and spices have been proposed, but only mineral salts provide the multi-functional properties related to processing, preservation, texture, hydration and water-binding. Other solutions have been used mostly in combination with mineral salts to achieve or retain the desired characteristics (Pedro and Nunes, 2019).

Several studies on sodium reduction in fish products can be found in the literature. They include investigations of a variety of species, e.g. cod, sea bass, salmon, trout and herring, and in many cases of smoked products. In one study, cod fillets were salted in brines with different pHs and saline compositions (Martínez-Alvarez et al., 2005). Sodium chloride was replaced by varying combinations of potassium chloride, calcium chloride and magnesium chloride. It was concluded that at pH 6.5 it was possible to replace 50 % of sodium chloride with potassium chloride without major alteration of the functional properties but at pH 8.5 the presence of potassium chloride negatively affected protein water-extractability resulting in increased hardness.

Fuentes et al. (2011) reported that replacement of 50 % sodium chloride with potassium chloride did not affect sensory scores, microbial counts, total volatile basic nitrogen, trimethylamine nitrogen or

thiobarbituric acid nitrogen in smoked sea bass. However, the formation of histamine, putrescine and cadaverine was delayed by using a mixture of the two salts. In another study of smoked sea bass, salted with 100 % sodium chloride and 50 % sodium chloride + 50 % potassium chloride, it was found that the type of salt did not affect the texture or other physicochemical parameters (Fuentes et al., 2012).

Smoked salmon products were evaluated in a quantitative descriptive analysis by a trained panel and in consumer tests (Almli and Hersleth, 2013). The results revealed that replacing one-third of sodium chloride by potassium chloride did not affect the sensory profile or the consumers' liking and their willingness to pay. However, it was also stated that it was unclear if the results could be generalised to other fish products, since the strong smoke flavour might have contributed to masking any sensory difference between products subjected to the two different salting methods.

Rizo et al. (2017) concluded that a sodium reduction of 42 % could be obtained in smoked trout by partial substitution of sodium chloride with potassium chloride without affecting shelf-life, physico-chemical quality or sensory acceptance.

In a comprehensive study by Giese et al. (2019), sodium chloride was replaced by various salt substitutes, including potassium chloride, potassium lactate and three different commercial salt substitutes in the production of two fish products, i.e. herring and cold-smoked salmon. The sodium content in herring could be reduced to almost half without resulting in any significant differences regarding aerobic and anaerobic mesophilic counts, organoleptic properties, texture, colour and growth of *Listeria monocytogenes*. Furthermore, a consumer test revealed that the consumers did not discriminate in liking between the reference product and the reformulated samples. For cold-smoked salmon, it was reported that samples with 50 % lower sodium content did not differ significantly from the reference product regarding odour, aerobic and anaerobic counts and growth of *Listeria monocytogenes*. However, it was also stated that the application of sodium reduction concepts always requires product-specific testing due to the variety of fish products with regard to raw material, processing, formulation and storage conditions.

Potassium chloride is the salt most frequently used to replace sodium chloride, but often leaves a bitter and metallic after-taste at high concentrations (Giese et al., 2019). Thus, in recent years, salt mixtures with lower sodium contents (approximately 35 % lower than sodium chloride) such as Pansalt®, Sub4salt®, Lo Salt® and Saltwell® have been tested and commercialized (Petit et al., 2019).

However, research focusing on substitution of sodium chloride alone with Saltwell®, a naturally occurring salt, originating from the Chilean desert, which contains a mixture of sodium and potassium chloride, on the formulation of seafood products were not found in the literature. For this reason, the aim of this study was to use mixtures of sodium chloride and Saltwell® (0, 40 and 80%) to investigate its potential to reduce sodium contents in seafood products without compromising quality and safety using salmon pâté as a model.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Production of salmon pâté

Salmon pâtés were produced at Stjärnlax, a small family-run company in Gothenburg (Sweden). The product contained the following; eggs, minced salmon, cream, sour cream, dill, salt, white pepper and water. The salmon was farmed and killed in Norway before being transported on ice to Stjärnlax where it was cleaned, filleted and minced.

In the three pâtés, the total salt content was 1.0 % (w/w). The original product contained common salt only (i.e. sodium chloride). To reduce the sodium content compared to the original product, different amounts of sodium chloride were substituted with Saltwell® (Salinity, Gothenburg, Sweden). Saltwell® constitutes a natural mixture of sodium chloride and potassium chloride and contains approximately 35 % less sodium per gram than common salt (sodium chloride).

Three pâté formulations were produced, in three batches each, the compositions of thewith different salt-mixtures are presented in of salt (table 1). ~~Three batches were produced for each pâté.~~

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Table 1. Salt composition of pâtés in the study.

Sample	Salt composition
A	100 % sodium chloride (reference product)
B	60 % sodium chloride + 40 % Saltwell®
C	20 % sodium chloride + 80 % Saltwell®

The salmon pâtés were produced by mixing all the ingredients in an industrial homogenizer at 4°C. These mixtures were placed in aluminium trays and baked at 125°C for 40 minutes and cooled in a refrigerated room (-2°C) until the core product temperature was 8°C. Thereafter, the pâtés, each weighing 250 g, were vacuum packed and stored at 8°C until analysis.

2.2 Microbiological, water activity, water content and pH analyses

Pâtés (A-C) were portioned (25 g pâté) ~~in a sterile environment using sterile tools according to NMKL (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis) method No 91 (2010). Each portion was and~~ repackaged under vacuum according to NMKL (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis) method no 91 (2010). ~~in a sterile plastic for this purpose.~~ The packages were placed in an incubator at +8°C ~~together with a temperature logger.~~

Pâtés were evaluated for total aerobic counts and lactic acid bacteria according to NMKL methods 86 (2013) and 140 (2007) on day 0, 18, 22, 29, 36, 43 and 57. Samples (25 g) were homogenized in 0.1% peptone solution. In addition, serial decimal dilutions were prepared from a 10⁻¹ dilution, as necessary. The plates were incubated on TSA (Tryptone Soya Agar, Oxoid Ltd, Basingstoke, England)

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at 30°C for 3 days for total aerobic counts, and on MRS (De Man, Rogosa and Sharp agar, Oxoid Ltd, Basingstoke, England) at 25°C for 5 days, under anaerobic conditions, for lactic acid bacteria. Three replicates in each group were analyzed. The bacterial count results were expressed as log₁₀.

In order to study the product microbiological safety, a challenge test with two *Listeria monocytogenes* strains was performed according to NMKL method No 136 (2010). The two strains were CCUG 32964, which is used as a quality control strain in the food industry, and a strain - SIK609, isolated from fish in 2008 at RISE). The strains, maintained previously in a cryopreservation system, were replicated on TSA medium at 35°C for 24 hours. Then, they were separately inoculated in 9 mL of BHI (Brain Heart Infusion, Becton Dickinson and Company, Sparks, USA) medium and incubated at 37°C for 20 hours. The strains were cold adapted in 9 mL BHI-broth at 15°C for 72 hours before being inoculated on the surface of the pâtés as a mixture at 2.1-2.3 log CFU/g pâté using 0.25 mL inoculum per 25 g portion. The inoculated samples were repackaged, vacuum-sealed and stored as described previously. The counts of *Listeria monocytogenes* in inoculated pâtés homogenates were determined on days 0, 2, 4, 8, 10, 12, 14, 17, 21 and 28 and in uninoculated samples on days 0 and 57. *Listeria monocytogenes* were grown on Compass *Listeria* agar (Biokar Diagnostics, Beauvais, France) at 37°C for 24-48 hours.

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~~In order to study the microbiological safety of the product, a challenge test with two *Listeria monocytogenes* strains was performed according to NMKL method No 136 (2010). These were CCUG 32964, which is used as a quality control strain in the food industry, and a natural strain (SIK609) isolated from fish in 2008 at RISE. The strains, maintained previously in a cryopreservation system, were recultured on TSA (Tryptone Soya Agar) at 35°C for 24 hours. They were inoculated separately in 9 mL of BHI (Brain Heart Infusion) medium and incubated at 37°C for 20 hours. The strains were cultured, cold-adapted, in 9 mL BHI-broth at 15°C for 72 hours before being inoculated on to the surface of the pâtés as a mixture at 2.1-2.3 log cfu/g pâté using 0.25 mL inoculum per 25 g portion. The inoculated samples were repackaged, vacuum sealed and stored as described previously.~~

~~When sampling, the vacuum-sealed 25 g portion was cut open and samples diluted 1/10 and homogenized in 0.1% peptone saline. Homogenates from uninoculated samples were used to determine the lactic acid bacteria count and total bacteria count.~~

~~For shelf life testing total aerobic and lactic acid bacteria counts were conducted on days 0, 18, 22, 29, 36, 43 and 57. For total counts, homogenates were grown on TSA at 30°C for 3 days and lactic acid bacteria were grown on MRS (De Man, Rogosa and Sharp) agar at 25°C for 5 days under anaerobic conditions, according to NMKL methods No 86 (2013) and 140 (2007), respectively.~~

~~The counts of *Listeria monocytogenes* in inoculated pâtés homogenates were determined on days 0, 2, 4, 8, 10, 12, 14, 17, 21 and 28. *Listeria monocytogenes* were grown on Compass Listeria agar at 37°C for 24-48 hours.~~

~~Triplicates from each sample were analyzed on each occasion. Additional dilutions were prepared with 0.1% peptone saline.~~

~~Enrichment using NMKL method No 136 (2010) for detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* was performed for uninoculated samples on days 0 and 57.~~

~~To assess microbial growth potential, pH, water content and water activity (a_w), water content and pH were measured on days 0 and 70. pH was measured instrumentally by inserting the pH electrode for solids (Hanna HI-8418, Hanna instruments, Ronchi di Villafranca, Italy) directly into samples. Three values were recorded for each sample. Water activity was determined using a water activity meter (Aqua Lab CX-2, Decagon Devices, Pullman, WA, USA), ~~analyses were carried out in duplicate.~~ Water content was measured by drying pâtés at 105±2°C. Analyses of water activity and water content were carried out in duplicate. pH was measured instrumentally by inserting the pH electrode for solids (Hanna HI-8418, Hanna instruments, Ronchi di Villafranca, Italy) directly into samples. Three values were recorded for each sample.~~

2.3 Sensory analyses

Ten panellists from RISE’s external analytical sensory panel participated in the sensory evaluation. The panellists were selected according to internal guidelines consisting of the Ishihara test on colour deficiency, odour identification, basic taste identification, detection and measurement of reproducibility. All panellists were trained and had a common understanding of attributes used for generic descriptive analysis in accordance with [EN ISO 13299:2016\(en\)](#). The attributes were based on sensory perception of the appearance, texture with a knife, odour, mouthfeel/texture in the mouth, taste and flavour with the option to add attributes regarding residual/aftertaste. The selected attributes are presented in table 2.

Table 2. The selected attributes that were judged by the panellists. The intensities of the attributes were judged on a scale from absence (0) to high ranging (100) from 0 to 100.

Type of observation	Attribute
Appearance	Porosity
Texture with knife	Porosity
	Coherent texture
Odour	Total odour
	Fresh odour
	Canned fish odour

Mouthfeel	Juiciness
Taste and flavour	Total flavour
	Saltiness
	Acidity
	Canned fish flavour
	Residual/aftertaste

The sensory analyses started with an adaptation session where each attribute was tested individually and discussed by all panellists to reach a consensus about the meaning of the attribute and its definitions, the scales for each attribute were also agreed by the panel during this adaptation session. Samples from three batches of each pâté (A-C) were served. In addition to the nine samples (A1, A2, A3, B1, B2, B3, C1, C2 and C3) an extra A1 sample was served to obtain a measure of panel performance. The analyses were performed in duplicate (i.e. in total 20 different samples were evaluated by each panel member). The samples were served in a randomized order on white paper plates, see figure 1. Five samples were served at a time and there was a pause before the next five samples were served. The samples were coded using three-digit numbers.

Figure 1. Coded samples of salmon pâté served on paper plates.

The panellists evaluated each attribute on a scale ranging from 0 to 100, but the panellists also had the option to indicate other flavours and add comments, e.g. panellists described any aftertaste in their own words. Water and neutral wafers for cleansing the palette were available during the evaluations.

2.4 Chemical analyses

For determination of sodium (Na) and potassium (K) contents, the pâtés were homogenized using a mixer. Concentrations of sodium and potassium were determined using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry, ICP-OES, (Optima 8300, Perkin Elmer, Walyham, MA, USA) according to general principles in EN ISO 11885 after microwave digestion (Start D, Milestone Srl, Sorisole, Italy)

in acid according to general principles in EN 13656 where the acid composition was modified to fit sample compositions. Three replicates were analysed for each pâté from each batch, i.e. nine measurements were made.

Analyses of moisture, ash, free fat and protein were done in duplicate following the standard method of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (2000). The moisture content was quantified by drying pâtés at $105\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and the ash content by incineration of dried pâtés at $550\pm 15^\circ\text{C}$ until a constant weight was achieved. Free fat was extracted using diethyl ether as a solvent in a Soxhlet apparatus (Behr Labor-Technik, Düsseldorf, Germany) (7 h, approximately 40°C). Fat content was determined by weighing the residue after drying at $105\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Crude protein content was analysed by the Kjeldahl method ~~(AOAC, 2000)~~.

Cholesterol concentrations were determined by gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (Agilent gas chromatograph 6890 equipped with an electronically controlled split/splitless injection port and interfaced to a MSD-5973N mass selective detector, Little Falls, DE, USA) according to Cunha et al. (2006). Lactic acid was analysed by high performance liquid chromatography (Jasco equipped with a PU quaternary pump, Jasco AS-950 automatic sampler with a 10 μl loop and UV detector, Tokyo, Japan) according to Cunha et al. (2001).

2.5 Statistical analyses

Statistical evaluations of the microbiological ~~and physico-chemical~~ analyses were made using the Student's t-test comparing three replicates, both technical (from the same pâté) and biological (from different pâtés of the same formulation), ~~while~~ sensory data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the Tukey HSD test using EyeOpenR in EyeQuestion. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$ for all analyses.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Microbiological, water activity, water content and pH analyses

~~Amount of naturally occurring bacteria in the salmon pâtés differed among samples and within samples (1-3). However, there were no significant differences found among samples A, B and C. Total aerobic counts obtained during storage are presented in figure 2. This count was slightly above 1.0 log cfu/g at the start of storage. The growth rate was similar in all three pâtés and no significant differences were observed at any of the sampling times. After 36 days of storage the average count of total aerobic microorganisms was approximately 6.5 log cfu/g in the three pâtés, and the growth curve appeared to have reached some sort of a plateau. In the EU there is no defined limit for the total count of microorganisms in foods but for cold foods, including salmon pâté, generally levels up to log 7.0-7.5 will not result in spoilage or reduction in shelf life (Swedish Food Agency, 1998; Synlab, 2019). Thus, our results indicated that all samples had a shelf life of at least 57 days, i.e. more than the expected eight weeks.~~

Lactic acid bacteria were anticipated to be the most likely spoilage organisms, especially as the pâtés were vacuum packed (Adams and Moss, 2000). However, lactic acid bacteria were only found in ~~few samples~~ less than 10 % of the samples and were not ~~considered to be~~ the main spoilage organism detected in this product. No pattern could be identified between samples containing lactic acid bacteria as they appeared randomly both between sample types and sampling times. However, in cases where lactic acid bacteria were found, amounts were high (3.1-8.3 log cfu/g) indicating good conditions for lactic acid bacteria to grow, if such bacteria are present.

No ~~naturally occurring~~ *L. monocytogenes* were found in the samples analysed, at day 0 or at the end of the ~~shelf-life~~ storage.

Figure 2. ~~Growth of naturally occurring aerobic bacteria~~Total aerobic counts in salmon pâtés during storage at +8°C. Sample A (light gray) - 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B (mid-gray) - 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C (dark gray) - 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Each bar represents the mean value of three batches and three analytical replicates (9 measurements in total). Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

~~Data from measurements of water activity, water content and pH are presented in figures 3-5.~~ There were no significant differences in water contents or water activities during storage (figures 3 and 4). However, pH was significantly lower on day 70 than on day 0 in all pâtés (figure 5). ~~The reduction in pH has been probably~~ associated to acid production by spoilage flora ~~(as observed by Adams and Moss, 2000).~~ ~~However, this was not verified in the study.~~

Figure 3. Water activity (a_w) in salmon pâtés at day 0 (dark gray) and day 70 (light gray) of ~~the shelf life study~~ storage. Sample A (light gray)– 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B (mid-gray)– 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C (dark gray)– 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Bars from day 0 represents the mean value from three batches and bars from day 70 represents the mean value of three batches and two analytical replicates (6 measurements in total). The standard deviations were too small to be visualized in the graph.

Figure 4. Water content in salmon pâtés at day 0 (dark gray) and day 70 (light gray) of ~~the shelf life study~~ storage. Sample A (light gray)– 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B (mid-gray)– 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C (dark gray)– 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. All bars represent the mean

value of three batches and two analytical replicates (6 measurements in total). The standard deviations were too small to be visualized in the graph.

Figure 5. pH in salmon pâtés at day 0 (dark gray) and day 70 (light gray) of ~~the shelf life study~~ storage. Sample A (light gray)– 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B (mid-gray)– 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C (dark gray)– 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Bars from day 0 represents the mean value of three batches (3 measurements in total) and bars from day 70 represents the mean value of three batches and three analytical replicates (9 measurements). The standard deviations on day 0 were too small to be visualized in the graph.

Results from the challenge tests with *L. monocytogenes* are presented in figure 6 and show that there was no barrier limiting growth of *Listeria* in the salmon pâtés. Growth of *L. monocytogenes* was rapid, about 0.8 log cfu/day, calculated from the exponential phase of the growth curve. Thus, even if sampling of the products was routinely below detection (1 cfu *L. monocytogenes* in 25 g), this species might grow from <1 cfu/25 g to 2 log cfu/g product in about 5 days. Since the product is not heat-treated prior to consumption, microbiological safety with respect to *L. monocytogenes* would need to be controlled by extensive environmental sampling, showing this species is not present in either the production plant or in the product. Since most salmon pâtés are heat-treated, cooled down and vacuum packed, it would be better if reduced sodium salmon pâtés, such as described here, were heat-

treated in their packaging reducing re-contamination and controlling risks associated with *L. monocytogenes*.

Statistical evaluation using the Student's t-test showed there were no differences among pâtés A, B and C or at any sampling points within pâtés. Thus, the growth of *L. monocytogenes* was not influenced by replacing up to 80 % of sodium chloride with Saltwell®, as long as the total amount of salt was maintained.

Figure 6. Growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* in salmon pâtés during storage at +8°C. Sample A (light gray) - 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B (mid-gray) - 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C (dark gray) - 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

In summary, the microbial growth in pâtés A, B and C was similar indicating there were no negative effects on ~~shelf life or~~ microbiological safety or quality of the reduced-salt salmon pâtés when up to 80 % of sodium chloride was replaced with Saltwell®. ~~The expected shelf life of the product was at least eight weeks if kept at or below 8°C, regardless of composition.~~

3.2 Sensory analyses

Results from the sensory analyses are presented in table 3. A more visual presentation of results is shown in a spider plot (figure 7). As can be seen in figure 7, lines overlapped to a large extent, indicating the products had very similar sensory profiles.

Indeed, for most attributes there were no significant differences among the pâtés (A-C). However, for three attributes there were minor differences that were statistically significant, saltiness was the most interesting attribute since differences among the samples were associated with salt composition.

Table 3. Mean values and standard error (in brackets) of panellists' evaluations of selected attributes for salmon pâtés. Each value is based on 60 evaluations, 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for pâtés A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®). Results that were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) are indicated by superscript letters. The letters indicate which sample is significantly different.

Attribute	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Porosity (appearance)	52 (3)	49 (3)	52 (3)
Porosity (texture)	42 (2)	47 (3)	43 (3)
Coherent texture	72 (2) ^{b, c}	64 (2) ^a	65 (2) ^a
Total odour	46 (3)	48 (3)	48 (3)
Fresh odour	39 (2)	41 (3)	41 (2)
Canned fish odour	30 (3)	31 (3)	31 (3)
Juiciness	56 (3)	54 (3)	56 (3)

Total flavour	59 (2)	58 (2)	55 (2)
Saltiness	55 (3) ^c	52 (2)	45 (3) ^a
Acidity	40 (2)	40 (3)	39 (2)
Canned fish flavour	30 (2) ^c	32 (3)	36 (3) ^a
Residual/aftertaste	26 (3)	28 (3)	29 (3)

Figure 7. Spider plot of the mean values of the panellists' evaluations of the selected attributes for the different samples. Each mean value is based on 60 evaluations, 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for samples A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B – 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C – 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®).

There was an indication from the panel that saltiness decreased as sodium chloride was substituted with Saltwell®. The difference in saltiness between pâté A (100 % sodium chloride) and pâté C (20 % sodium chloride + 80 % Saltwell®) was significant, if small, with the mean value dropping from 55 to 45 on a scale 0 to 100. The saltiness of pâté B (60 % sodium chloride + 40 % Saltwell®) was not significantly different from either of the other two pâtés. There was also a significant difference between pâtés A and C regarding canned fish flavour, with pâté C having a slightly higher intensity of that flavour. Finally, pâté A scored more with respect to coherent texture than pâtés B and C. Again, the differences were small, with the value being approximately 10 % higher for pâté A.

The panellists were asked to use their words to describe any flavours other than those specifically mentioned in the questionnaire and their comments that are summarized in table 4.

Table 4. Describing comments of other flavours observed by the panellists. Number of comments of the different flavours made for the three pâtés. A total of 60 evaluations were made for each pâté as 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for samples A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®).

Other flavours	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Pepper/white pepper	15	18	18
Dill	7	3	6
Metallic	2	3	5
Egg	1	0	1
Salmon	2	0	0
Crayfish	0	1	1
Fish cake	0	0	2

Bitter	0	0	1
Stale	0	1	0
Umami	0	0	1
Hay	1	0	0
Lemon	0	1	0

The most common remarks were those related to pepper/white pepper flavour. This is not surprising given white pepper was one of the ingredients used. Similarly, dill was also an ingredient and consequently its flavour was remarked upon by the panellists. The most interesting comment was, however, the metallic flavour, since this feature is often associated with substitution of sodium with potassium. However, few panellists remarked upon this, in total just 10 out of the 180 evaluations. Furthermore, the observations of a metallic flavour were distributed evenly among the three pâtés (A-C) and there were no indications that such a flavour would pose a palatability problem for consumers. The panellists were also asked to use their words to describe any residual/aftertaste, these comments are summarized in table 5.

Table 5. Describing comments of the residual/aftertaste made by panellists. Number of comments of the different observations made for the three pâtés. A total of 60 evaluations were made for each pâté as 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for pâtés A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®).

Residual/aftertaste	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Pepper/white pepper	12	14	10

Dill	5	12	6
Metallic flavour	5	2	6
Fish cake/canned fish	5	2	3
Butter flavour	2	3	2
Intense aftertaste	0	5	2
Bitter	0	2	2
Fat	0	2	2
Cayenne pepper	1	1	1
Cream	1	2	0
Fish/salmon	0	3	0
Aromatic/spices	2	1	0
Acidity	2	0	0
Mild aftertaste	1	0	1
Salt	1	0	0
Hay	1	0	0
Crayfish	1	0	0
Short aftertaste	1	0	0
Stale	0	1	0
Fish flavour	0	0	1

The most frequent observations regarding aftertaste were related to pepper/white pepper and dill. Metallic flavour was the third most frequent comment but such observations were few. In addition, the metallic flavour was noted in all the three pâtés but there was no indication that samples containing Saltwell® were significantly different from the sodium chloride only pâté (A) or that increased potassium gave rise to metallic aftertaste more often.

Evaluation of sensory panel performance showed agreement and reproducibility of analyses were good for a majority of attributes, most p-values were above 0.15 for both agreement and reproducibility, meaning the panel performed well. Discrimination among samples was bad, indicating it was difficult to separate the pâtés from each other, i.e. sensory characteristics were very similar. Differences among the pâtés were so small that the influence of the individuals on the panel was greater than judges was larger than those of pâté composition. In other words, there was a larger variation in individual evaluations by panellists than perceived in samples, regardless of Saltwell® substitution. Thus, the results from the sensory study were encouraging as they suggested sodium chloride might be partially substituted with Saltwell® without any major impact on sensory perception of the product by consumers.

3.3 Chemical analyses

The results for the chemical analyses are presented in tables 6 and 7.

Unsurprisingly, there were no significant differences in the contents of moisture, ash, fat protein, cholesterol or lactic acid among the three pâtés, since the only difference was in the type of added salt.

Table 6. Moisture, ash and fat content (%) in the three pâtés (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®). Mean values and standard deviations are based on nine measurements of each sample.

Analysis	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Moisture (%)	66.2±0.4	65.8±0.6	65.5±0.2
Ash (%)	1.91±0.01	1.93±0.02	1.91±0.02
Fat (%)	17.6±0.3	18.3±0.3	18.5±0.2
Protein (%)	13.3±0.3	13.2±0.5	13.4±0.6
Cholesterol (mg/100 g)	29.9±2.2	28.0±2.8	31.1±1.2
Lactic acid (mg/100 g)	40.1±2.2	44.4±4.7	42.0±1.7

Table 7. Sodium and potassium content (g/kg) in the three different samples (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®). Mean values and standard deviations are based on nine measurements of each sample.

Analysis	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C
Sodium (g/kg)	5.1±0.1	4.5±0.1	4.0±0.1
Potassium (g/kg)	2.6±0.1	3.3±0.1	3.9±0.1

The objective of the study was to reduce sodium content in the salmon pâtés. The results verified that sodium was reduced in pâtés B and C compared with the reference product (pâté A), and a corresponding increase of potassium concentrations. The reduction in pâté B was 12 % less sodium and in pâté C 22 % less sodium. Obviously, this was in accordance with substitution of common salt with Saltwell®, which has a lower sodium and a higher potassium content. It is worth noting that although a large proportion of the sodium present in the final product originated from added salt, other ingredients, especially salmon and eggs, also contributed to the total amount of sodium (e.g. pâté C contained 80 % Saltwell®, which equated to a 28 % reduction in added sodium, but the final product contained only 22 % less sodium).-

4 Conclusions

Saltwell®, a naturally occurring salt containing a mixture of sodium chloride and potassium chloride, was used to substitute sodium chloride in reduced sodium salmon pâté. The microbiological and nutritional qualities of the product were maintained while the sodium content was reduced by 22 %. Sensory profiles of the reduced sodium product and the original common salt product were very similar. Significant differences were observed for three of the twelve attributes studied (coherent texture, saltiness, canned fish flavor), but these differences were very small.

In conclusion, Saltwell® represents a viable alternative to sodium chloride in the formulation of salmon pâtés, and can be used to reduce sodium content. The results obtained revealed clearly that microbiological safety as well as important sensory and physicochemical properties, were maintained in reduced sodium pâtés, and thus ~~that the shelf-life was~~ quality was similar to that of the original product.

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1 Introduction

Excess salt (sodium chloride, NaCl) consumption increases the risk of hypertension (high blood pressure) which is associated with increased risk of cardiovascular disease (Grillo et al., 2019). More specifically, high sodium intake is one of the most important health challenges in relation to processed food products. It affects public health in a negative manner leading to considerable economical costs for society (Global Burden of Disease, 2019), but salt is also a necessary ingredient for palatability and preservation. The World Health Organization (WHO) and national authorities worldwide have issued recommendations for sodium consumption, specifically that sodium intakes for adults and children should be less than 2 g sodium per day, which is equivalent to 5 g of sodium chloride (WHO, 2012). The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Panel on Nutrition, Novel Foods and Allergens (NDA) (2019) also considered that 2 g sodium per day is safe and adequate for the general adult population, but consumption in most European Member States is close to twice this. For this reason, WHO and EU have agreed a global target to reduce population sodium intake by 30 % until 2025 for the prevention and control of non-communicable diseases (WHO, 2018).

Approximately 75 % of the sodium intake originates from foods that are processed by the food industry or prepared for consumption in restaurants. The remainder (25 %) occurs naturally in foods or from salt added during cooking or at the table (Allison and Fouladkhah, 2018). In order to meet demands from both authorities and consumers, and be competitive, there is a strong need for the food industry to be able to offer reformulated products with lower sodium contents.

However, common or table salt is a crucial food ingredient that has many important functions, and it is a challenge for the food industry to reduce sodium concentrations in processed products, without compromising sensory properties (e.g. taste, flavour and texture), microbial safety, shelf-life and processability. The most obvious impact of salt is the salty taste, but it is also added for preservation. Salt lowers water activity, thereby affecting the growth of both spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms and, thus, extending shelf-life (Cepanec et al., 2017; Giese et al., 2019).

All unprocessed seafood contains some sodium at low concentrations. The sodium content of raw fish is typically 25-150 mg per 100 g (Pedro and Nunes, 2019). Sodium concentrations in processed seafoods vary substantially among products and countries, reflecting dietary habits and preferences. Large variations in salt contents can also be observed in foods from the same group, as is the case for salted and dried (around 2000-3000 mg per 100 g), canned (32-6000 mg per 100 g) and smoked (500-1100 mg per 100 g) fish products (Webster et al., 2010; Pedro and Nunes, 2019).

The application of well-defined strategies that might allow reduction of sodium in processed seafood products, while maintaining their quality, shelf-life, consumer acceptability and regulatory compliance, is of utmost importance. Mineral salts, taste modifiers and taste enhancers as well as herbs and spices have been proposed, but only mineral salts provide the multi-functional properties related to processing, preservation, texture, hydration and water-binding. Other solutions have been used mostly in combination with mineral salts to achieve or retain the desired characteristics (Pedro and Nunes, 2019).

Several studies on sodium reduction in fish products can be found in the literature. They include investigations of a variety of species, e.g. cod, sea bass, salmon, trout and herring, and in many cases of smoked products. In one study, cod fillets were salted in brines with different pHs and saline compositions (Martínez-Alvarez et al., 2005). Sodium chloride was replaced by varying combinations of potassium chloride, calcium chloride and magnesium chloride. It was concluded that at pH 6.5 it was possible to replace 50 % of sodium chloride with potassium chloride without major alteration of the functional properties but at pH 8.5 the presence of potassium chloride negatively affected protein water-extractability resulting in increased hardness.

Fuentes et al. (2011) reported that replacement of 50 % sodium chloride with potassium chloride did not affect sensory scores, microbial counts, total volatile basic nitrogen, trimethylamine nitrogen or thiobarbituric acid nitrogen in smoked sea bass. However, the formation of histamine, putrescine and cadaverine was delayed by using a mixture of the two salts. In another study of smoked sea bass, salted

with 100 % sodium chloride and 50 % sodium chloride + 50 % potassium chloride, it was found that the type of salt did not affect the texture or other physicochemical parameters (Fuentes et al., 2012).

Smoked salmon products were evaluated in a quantitative descriptive analysis by a trained panel and in consumer tests (Almli and Hersleth, 2013). The results revealed that replacing one-third of sodium chloride by potassium chloride did not affect the sensory profile or the consumers' liking and their willingness to pay. However, it was also stated that it was unclear if the results could be generalised to other fish products, since the strong smoke flavour might have contributed to masking any sensory difference between products subjected to the two different salting methods.

Rizo et al. (2017) concluded that a sodium reduction of 42 % could be obtained in smoked trout by partial substitution of sodium chloride with potassium chloride without affecting shelf-life, physico-chemical quality or sensory acceptance.

In a comprehensive study by Giese et al. (2019), sodium chloride was replaced by various salt substitutes, including potassium chloride, potassium lactate and three different commercial salt substitutes in the production of two fish products, i.e. herring and cold-smoked salmon. The sodium content in herring could be reduced to almost half without resulting in any significant differences regarding aerobic and anaerobic mesophilic counts, organoleptic properties, texture, colour and growth of *Listeria monocytogenes*. Furthermore, a consumer test revealed that the consumers did not discriminate in liking between the reference product and the reformulated samples. For cold-smoked salmon, it was reported that samples with 50 % lower sodium content did not differ significantly from the reference product regarding odour, aerobic and anaerobic counts and growth of *Listeria monocytogenes*. However, it was also stated that the application of sodium reduction concepts always requires product-specific testing due to the variety of fish products with regard to raw material, processing, formulation and storage conditions.

Potassium chloride is the salt most frequently used to replace sodium chloride, but often leaves a bitter and metallic after-taste at high concentrations (Giese et al., 2019). Thus, in recent years, salt mixtures

with lower sodium contents (approximately 35 % lower than sodium chloride) such as Pansalt®, Sub4salt®, Lo Salt® and Saltwell® have been tested and commercialized (Petit et al., 2019).

However, research focusing on substitution of sodium chloride alone with Saltwell®, a naturally occurring salt, originating from the Chilean desert, which contains a mixture of sodium and potassium chloride, on the formulation of seafood products were not found in the literature. For this reason, the aim of this study was to use mixtures of sodium chloride and Saltwell® (0, 40 and 80%) to investigate its potential to reduce sodium contents in seafood products without compromising quality and safety using salmon pâté as a model.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Production of salmon pâté

Salmon pâtés were produced at Stjärnlax, a small family-run company in Gothenburg (Sweden). The product contained the following; eggs, minced salmon, cream, sour cream, dill, salt, white pepper and water. The salmon was farmed and killed in Norway before being transported on ice to Stjärnlax where it was cleaned, filleted and minced.

In the three pâtés, the total salt content was 1.0 % (w/w). The original product contained common salt only (i.e. sodium chloride). To reduce the sodium content compared to the original product, different amounts of sodium chloride were substituted with Saltwell® (Salinity, Gothenburg, Sweden). Saltwell® constitutes a natural mixture of sodium chloride and potassium chloride and contains approximately 35 % less sodium per gram than common salt (sodium chloride).

Three pâté formulations were produced, in three batches each, with different mixtures of salt (table 1).

Table 1. Salt composition of pâtés in the study.

Sample	Salt composition
A	100 % sodium chloride (reference product)
B	60 % sodium chloride + 40 % Saltwell®
C	20 % sodium chloride + 80 % Saltwell®

The salmon pâtés were produced by mixing all the ingredients in an industrial homogenizer at 4°C. These mixtures were placed in aluminium trays and baked at 125°C for 40 minutes and cooled in a refrigerated room (-2°C) until the core product temperature was 8°C. Thereafter, the pâtés, each weighing 250 g, were vacuum packed and stored at 8°C until analysis.

2.2 Microbiological, water activity, water content and pH analyses

Pâtés (A-C) were portioned (25 g pâté) and repackaged under vacuum according to NMKL (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis) method no 91 (2010).. The packages were placed in an incubator at +8°C.

Pâtés were evaluated for total aerobic counts and lactic acid bacteria according to NMKL methods 86 (2013) and 140 (2007) on day 0, 18, 22, 29, 36, 43 and 57. Samples (25 g) were homogenized in 0.1% peptone solution. In addition, serial decimal dilutions were prepared from a 10⁻¹ dilution, as necessary. The plates were incubated on TSA (Tryptone Soya Agar, Oxoid Ltd, Basingstoke, England) at 30°C for 3 days for total aerobic counts, and on MRS (De Man, Rogosa and Sharp agar, Oxoid Ltd, Basingstoke, England) at 25°C for 5 days, under anaerobic conditions, for lactic acid bacteria. Three replicates in each group were analyzed. The bacterial count results were expressed as log₁₀.

In order to study the product microbiological safety, a challenge test with two *Listeria monocytogenes* strains was performed according to NMKL method No 136 (2010). The two strains were CCUG 32964, which is used as a quality control strain in the food industry, and a strain - SIK609, isolated from fish in

2008 at RISE). The strains, maintained previously in a cryopreservation system, were replicated on TSA medium at 35°C for 24 hours. Then, they were separately inoculated in 9 mL of BHI (Brain Heart Infusion, Becton Dickinson and Company, Sparks, USA) medium and incubated at 37°C for 20 hours. The strains were cold adapted in 9 mL BHI-broth at 15°C for 72 hours before being inoculated on the surface of the pâtés as a mixture at 2.1-2.3 log CFU/g pâté using 0.25 mL inoculum per 25 g portion. The inoculated samples were repackaged, vacuum-sealed and stored as described previously. The counts of *Listeria monocytogenes* in inoculated pâtés homogenates were determined on days 0, 2, 4, 8, 10, 12, 14, 17, 21 and 28 and in uninoculated samples on days 0 and 57. *Listeria monocytogenes* were grown on Compass *Listeria* agar (Biokar Diagnostics, Beauvais, France) at 37°C for 24-48 hours. To assess microbial growth potential, water activity (a_w), water content and pH were measured on days 0 and 70. Water activity was determined using a water activity meter (Aqua Lab CX-2, Decagon Devices, Pullman, WA, USA). Water content was measured by drying pâtés at 105±2°C. Analyses of water activity and water content were carried out in duplicate. pH was measured instrumentally by inserting the pH electrode for solids (Hanna HI-8418, Hanna instruments, Ronchi di Villafranca, Italy) directly into samples. Three values were recorded for each sample.

2.3 Sensory analyses

Ten panellists from RISE's external analytical sensory panel participated in the sensory evaluation. The panellists were selected according to internal guidelines consisting of the Ishihara test on colour deficiency, odour identification, basic taste identification, detection and measurement of reproducibility. All panellists were trained and had a common understanding of attributes used for generic descriptive analysis in accordance with EN ISO 13299:2016. The attributes were based on sensory perception of the appearance, texture with a knife, odour, mouthfeel/texture in the mouth, taste and flavour with the option to add attributes regarding residual/aftertaste. The selected attributes are presented in table 2.

Table 2. The selected attributes that were judged by the panellists. The intensities of the attributes were judged on a scale from absence (0) to high ranging (100).

Type of observation	Attribute
Appearance	Porosity
Texture with knife	Porosity
	Coherent texture
Odour	Total odour
	Fresh odour
	Canned fish odour
Mouthfeel	Juiciness
Taste and flavour	Total flavour
	Saltiness
	Acidity
	Canned fish flavour
	Residual/aftertaste

The sensory analyses started with an adaptation session where each attribute was tested individually and discussed by all panellists to reach a consensus about the meaning of the attribute and its definitions, the scales for each attribute were also agreed by the panel during this adaptation session.

Samples from three batches of each pâté (A-C) were served. In addition to the nine samples (A1, A2, A3, B1, B2, B3, C1, C2 and C3) an extra A1 sample was served to obtain a measure of panel performance. The analyses were performed in duplicate (i.e. in total 20 different samples were evaluated by each panel member). The samples were served in a randomized order on white paper plates, see figure 1. Five samples were served at a time and there was a pause before the next five samples were served. The samples were coded using three-digit numbers.

Figure 1. Coded samples of salmon pâté served on paper plates.

The panellists evaluated each attribute on a scale ranging from 0 to 100, but the panellists also had the option to indicate other flavours and add comments, e.g. panellists described any aftertaste in their own words. Water and neutral wafers for cleansing the palette were available during the evaluations.

2.4 Chemical analyses

For determination of sodium (Na) and potassium (K) contents, the pâtés were homogenized using a mixer. Concentrations of sodium and potassium were determined using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry, ICP-OES, (Optima 8300, Perkin Elmer, Walyham, MA, USA) according to general principles in EN ISO 11885 after microwave digestion (Start D, Milestone Srl, Sorisole, Italy) in acid according to general principles in EN 13656 where the acid composition was modified to fit sample compositions. Three replicates were analysed for each pâté from each batch, i.e. nine measurements were made.

Analyses of moisture, ash, free fat and protein were done in duplicate following the standard method of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (2000). The moisture content was quantified by drying pâtés at $105\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the ash content by incineration of dried pâtés at $550\pm 15^{\circ}\text{C}$ until a constant weight was achieved. Free fat was extracted using diethyl ether as a solvent in a Soxhlet apparatus (Behr Labor-Technik, Düsseldorf, Germany) (7 h, approximately 40°C). Fat content was determined by weighing the residue after drying at $105\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Crude protein content was analysed by the Kjeldahl method.

Cholesterol concentrations were determined by gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (Agilent gas chromatograph 6890 equipped with an electronically controlled split/splitless injection port and interfaced to a MSD-5973N mass selective detector, Little Falls, DE, USA) according to Cunha et al. (2006). Lactic acid was analysed by high performance liquid chromatography (Jasco equipped with a PU quaternary pump, Jasco AS-950 automatic sampler with a 10 μl loop and UV detector, Tokyo, Japan) according to Cunha et al. (2001).

2.5 Statistical analyses

Statistical evaluations of the microbiological and physico-chemical analyses were made using the Student's t-test comparing three replicates, both technical (from the same pâté) and biological (from different pâtés of the same formulation). Sensory data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the Tukey HSD test using EyeOpenR in EyeQuestion. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$ for all analyses.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Microbiological, water activity, water content and pH analyses

Total aerobic counts obtained during storage are presented in figure 2. This count was slightly above 1.0 log cfu/g at the start of storage. The growth rate was similar in all three pâtés and no significant differences were observed at any of the sampling times. After 36 days of storage the average count of total aerobic microorganisms was approximately 6.5 log cfu/g in the three pâtés, and the growth curve appeared to have reached some sort of a plateau.

Lactic acid bacteria were anticipated to be the most likely spoilage organisms, especially as the pâtés were vacuum packed (Adams and Moss, 2000). However, lactic acid bacteria were only found in less than 10 % of the samples and were not considered to be the main spoilage organism detected in this product. No pattern could be identified between samples containing lactic acid bacteria as they appeared randomly both between sample types and sampling times. However, in cases where lactic acid bacteria were found, amounts were high (3.1-8.3 log cfu/g) indicating good conditions for lactic acid bacteria to grow, if such bacteria are present.

No *L. monocytogenes* were found in the samples analysed, at day 0 or at the end of the storage.

Figure 2. Total aerobic counts in salmon pâtés during storage at +8°C. Sample A (light gray) - 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B (mid-gray) - 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C (dark gray) - 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Each bar represents the mean value of three batches and three analytical replicates (9 measurements in total). Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

There were no significant differences in water contents or water activities during storage (figures 3 and 4). However, pH was significantly lower on day 70 than on day 0 in all pâtés (figure 5), probably associated to acid production by spoilage flora as observed by Adams and Moss, 2000.

Figure 3. Water activity (a_w) in salmon pâtés at day 0 (dark gray) and day 70 (light gray) of storage. Sample A - 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B - 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C - 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Bars from day 0 represents the mean value from three batches and bars from day 70 represents the mean value of three batches and two analytical replicates (6 measurements in total). The standard deviations were too small to be visualized in the graph.

Figure 4. Water content in salmon pâtés at day 0 (dark gray) and day 70 (light gray) of storage. Sample A - 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B - 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C - 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. All bars represent the mean value of three batches and two analytical replicates (6 measurements in total). The standard deviations were too small to be visualized in the graph.

Figure 5. pH in salmon pâtés at day 0 (dark gray) and day 70 (light gray) of storage. Sample A - 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B - 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C - 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Bars from day 0 represents the mean value of three batches (3 measurements in total) and bars from day 70 represents the mean value of three batches and three analytical replicates (9 measurements). The standard deviations on day 0 were too small to be visualized in the graph.

Results from the challenge tests with *L. monocytogenes* are presented in figure 6 and show that there was no barrier limiting growth of *Listeria* in the salmon pâtés. Growth of *L. monocytogenes* was rapid, about 0.8 log cfu/day, calculated from the exponential phase of the growth curve. Thus, even if sampling of the products was routinely below detection (1 cfu *L. monocytogenes* in 25 g), this species might grow from <1 cfu/25 g to 2 log cfu/g product in about 5 days. Since the product is not heat-treated prior to consumption, microbiological safety with respect to *L. monocytogenes* would need to be controlled by extensive environmental sampling, showing this species is not present in either the production plant or in the product. Since most salmon pâtés are heat-treated, cooled down and vacuum packed, it would be better if reduced sodium salmon pâtés, such as described here, were heat-treated in their packaging reducing re-contamination and controlling risks associated with *L. monocytogenes*.

Statistical evaluation using the Student's t-test showed there were no differences among pâtés A, B and C or at any sampling points within pâtés. Thus, the growth of *L. monocytogenes* was not influenced

by replacing up to 80 % of sodium chloride with Saltwell®, as long as the total amount of salt was maintained.

Figure 6. Growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* in salmon pâtés during storage at +8°C. Sample A (light gray) - 100 % NaCl (reference product), sample B (mid-gray) - 60 % NaCl + 40 % Saltwell®, and sample C (dark gray) - 20 % NaCl + 80 % Saltwell®. Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

In summary, the microbial growth in pâtés A, B and C was similar indicating there were no negative effects on microbiological safety or quality of the reduced-salt salmon pâtés when up to 80 % of sodium chloride was replaced with Saltwell®.

3.2 Sensory analyses

Results from the sensory analyses are presented in table 3. A more visual presentation of results is shown in a spider plot (figure 7). As can be seen in figure 7, lines overlapped to a large extent, indicating the products had very similar sensory profiles.

Indeed, for most attributes there were no significant differences among the pâtés (A-C). However, for three attributes there were minor differences that were statistically significant, saltiness was the most interesting attribute since differences among the samples were associated with salt composition.

Table 3. Mean values and standard error (in brackets) of panellists' evaluations of selected attributes for salmon pâtés. Each value is based on 60 evaluations, 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for pâtés A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®). Results that were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) are indicated by superscript letters. The letters indicate which sample is significantly different.

Attribute	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Porosity (appearance)	52 (3)	49 (3)	52 (3)
Porosity (texture)	42 (2)	47 (3)	43 (3)
Coherent texture	72 (2) ^{b, c}	64 (2) ^a	65 (2) ^a
Total odour	46 (3)	48 (3)	48 (3)
Fresh odour	39 (2)	41 (3)	41 (2)
Canned fish odour	30 (3)	31 (3)	31 (3)
Juiciness	56 (3)	54 (3)	56 (3)
Total flavour	59 (2)	58 (2)	55 (2)
Saltiness	55 (3) ^c	52 (2)	45 (3) ^a
Acidity	40 (2)	40 (3)	39 (2)
Canned fish flavour	30 (2) ^c	32 (3)	36 (3) ^a
Residual/aftertaste	26 (3)	28 (3)	29 (3)

Figure 7. Spider plot of the mean values of the panellists' evaluations of the selected attributes for the different samples. Each mean value is based on 60 evaluations, 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for samples A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®).

There was an indication from the panel that saltiness decreased as sodium chloride was substituted with Saltwell®. The difference in saltiness between pâté A (100 % sodium chloride) and pâté C (20 % sodium chloride + 80 % Saltwell®) was significant, if small, with the mean value dropping from 55 to 45 on a scale 0 to 100. The saltiness of pâté B (60 % sodium chloride + 40 % Saltwell®) was not significantly different from either of the other two pâtés. There was also a significant difference between pâtés A and C regarding canned fish flavour, with pâté C having a slightly higher intensity of

that flavour. Finally, pâté A scored more with respect to coherent texture than pâtés B and C. Again, the differences were small, with the value being approximately 10 % higher for pâté A.

The panellists were asked to use their words to describe any flavours other than those specifically mentioned in the questionnaire and their comments that are summarized in table 4.

Table 4. Describing comments of other flavours observed by the panellists. Number of comments of the different flavours made for the three pâtés. A total of 60 evaluations were made for each pâté as 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for samples A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®).

Other flavours	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Pepper/white pepper	15	18	18
Dill	7	3	6
Metallic	2	3	5
Egg	1	0	1
Salmon	2	0	0
Crayfish	0	1	1
Fish cake	0	0	2
Bitter	0	0	1
Stale	0	1	0
Umami	0	0	1
Hay	1	0	0
Lemon	0	1	0

The most common remarks were those related to pepper/white pepper flavour. This is not surprising given white pepper was one of the ingredients used. Similarly, dill was also an ingredient and consequently its flavour was remarked upon by the panellists. The most interesting comment was, however, the metallic flavour, since this feature is often associated with substitution of sodium with potassium. However, few panellists remarked upon this, in total just 10 out of the 180 evaluations. Furthermore, the observations of a metallic flavour were distributed evenly among the three pâtés (A-C) and there were no indications that such a flavour would pose a palatability problem for consumers. The panellists were also asked to use their words to describe any residual/aftertaste, these comments are summarized in table 5.

Table 5. Describing comments of the residual/aftertaste made by panellists. Number of comments of the different observations made for the three pâtés. A total of 60 evaluations were made for each pâté as 10 panellists performed duplicate testing of samples from three different batches for pâtés A, B and C (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®).

Residual/aftertaste	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Pepper/white pepper	12	14	10
Dill	5	12	6
Metallic flavour	5	2	6
Fish cake/canned fish	5	2	3
Butter flavour	2	3	2
Intense aftertaste	0	5	2

Bitter	0	2	2
Fat	0	2	2
Cayenne pepper	1	1	1
Cream	1	2	0
Fish/salmon	0	3	0
Aromatic/spices	2	1	0
Acidity	2	0	0
Mild aftertaste	1	0	1
Salt	1	0	0
Hay	1	0	0
Crayfish	1	0	0
Short aftertaste	1	0	0
Stale	0	1	0
Fish flavour	0	0	1

The most frequent observations regarding aftertaste were related to pepper/white pepper and dill. Metallic flavour was the third most frequent comment but such observations were few. In addition, the metallic flavour was noted in all the three pâtés but there was no indication that samples containing Saltwell® were significantly different from the sodium chloride only pâté (A) or that increased potassium gave rise to metallic aftertaste more often.

Evaluation of sensory panel performance showed agreement and reproducibility of analyses were good for a majority of attributes, most p-values were above 0.15 for both agreement and reproducibility, meaning the panel performed well. Discrimination among samples was bad, indicating it was difficult to separate the pâtés from each other, i.e. sensory characteristics were very similar. Differences among the pâtés were so small that the influence of the individuals on the panel was greater than judges was larger than those of pâté composition. In other words, there was a larger variation in individual evaluations by panellists than perceived in samples, regardless of Saltwell® substitution. Thus, the results from the sensory study were encouraging as they suggested sodium chloride might be partially substituted with Saltwell® without any major impact on sensory perception of the product by consumers.

3.3 Chemical analyses

The results for the chemical analyses are presented in tables 6 and 7.

Unsurprisingly, there were no significant differences in the contents of moisture, ash, fat protein, cholesterol or lactic acid among the three pâtés, since the only difference was in the type of added salt.

Table 6. Moisture, ash and fat content (%) in the three pâtés (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®). Mean values and standard deviations are based on nine measurements of each sample.

Analysis	Pâté A	Pâté B	Pâté C
Moisture (%)	66.2±0.4	65.8±0.6	65.5±0.2

Ash (%)	1.91±0.01	1.93±0.02	1.91±0.02
Fat (%)	17.6±0.3	18.3±0.3	18.5±0.2
Protein (%)	13.3±0.3	13.2±0.5	13.4±0.6
Cholesterol (mg/100 g)	29.9±2.2	28.0±2.8	31.1±1.2
Lactic acid (mg/100 g)	40.1±2.2	44.4±4.7	42.0±1.7

Table 7. Sodium and potassium content (g/kg) in the three different samples (Pâté A – 100% NaCl; Pâté B - 60% NaCl + 40% Saltwell®; Pâté C - 20% NaCl + 80% Saltwell®). Mean values and standard deviations are based on nine measurements of each sample.

Analysis	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C
Sodium (g/kg)	5.1±0.1	4.5±0.1	4.0±0.1
Potassium (g/kg)	2.6±0.1	3.3±0.1	3.9±0.1

The objective of the study was to reduce sodium content in the salmon pâtés. The results verified that sodium was reduced in pâtés B and C compared with the reference product (pâté A), and a corresponding increase of potassium concentrations. The reduction in pâté B was 12 % less sodium and in pâté C 22 % less sodium. Obviously, this was in accordance with substitution of common salt with Saltwell®, which has a lower sodium and a higher potassium content. It is worth noting that although a large proportion of the sodium present in the final product originated from added salt,

other ingredients, especially salmon and eggs, also contributed to the total amount of sodium (e.g. pâté C contained 80 % Saltwell®, which equated to a 28 % reduction in added sodium, but the final product contained only 22 % less sodium).

4 Conclusions

Saltwell®, a naturally occurring salt containing a mixture of sodium chloride and potassium chloride, was used to substitute sodium chloride in reduced sodium salmon pâté. The microbiological and nutritional qualities of the product were maintained while the sodium content was reduced by 22 %. Sensory profiles of the reduced sodium product and the original common salt product were very similar. Significant differences were observed for three of the twelve attributes studied (coherent texture, saltiness, canned fish flavor), but these differences were very small.

In conclusion, Saltwell® represents a viable alternative to sodium chloride in the formulation of salmon pâtés, and can be used to reduce sodium content. The results obtained revealed clearly that microbiological safety as well as important sensory and physicochemical properties, were maintained in reduced sodium pâtés, and thus the quality was similar to that of the original product.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Highlights

- Sodium chloride was substituted with Saltwell® to produce salmon pâtés with reduced sodium content.
- Microbiological and nutritional qualities of salmon pâtés were maintained while the sodium content was reduced by 22 %.
- Sensory profiles of the reduced sodium salmon pâtés and the original common salt salmon pâtés were very similar.
- Saltwell® is an alternative to sodium chloride in the formulation of salmon pâtés and can be used to reduce sodium content.

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